

Solar Cell Defect Detection with YOLO v6

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, solar cell plays a key role in generating the renewable green energy. The performance of each cell depends on the structural integrity. During the manufacturing of the cell in the manufacturing units, various defects may be recognized including finger interruptions, dark spot, microcracks, etc. which can reduce life and performance of the solar cell. Traditionally, these defects are detected using manual inspection of each cell, which leads to time consuming and not accurate. To address these challenges ML and DL mechanism have been used for defect detection. However, this method also facing various challenges with respect to size, shape, illumination and texture of the defect detection. So, to overcome the challenges, the new system has been designed and developed for solar cell fault detection using YOLOv6. It uses the enhanced and multi-scale detection of the various category of the defects. The performance has been compared with the other mechanism such as YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN based on various evaluation parameters. The experimental evaluation on the elpv dataset shows that the accuracy achieves 99.04% which confirms the superiority of the model compared with other models. This proposed research provides the fast, reliable and automatic framework for improving manufacturing process of solar cell.

Keyword: - Solar Cell Defect Detection, Computer Vision, Deep Learning, YOLOv5, Faster R-CNN, Cross Stage Partial Network, YOLOv6, Deformable Convolution, Photovoltaic Inspection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar energy is evolving faster with the cost optimization which leads to one of the most sustainable sources of the clean and green renewable energy generation. The solar cell is a mostly used key component for generating the solar energy also called as photovoltaic cell. The reliability and efficiency of the solar energy generation heavily depend on the integrity and quality of the solar cells. Minor defects degrade the performance drastically, which is the critical factor in the manufacturing process. The solar cell manufacturing involves the various steps including, water slicing, texture of surface, doping, coating for anti-reflection, metallization and lamination of solar cell. During this process defects may occur due to mechanical error, human handling or temperature exposure. Such defects are not visible to the eyes. Traditionally, manual visual inspection along with semi-automated method has been used for defect detection. But it suffers from the various limitations including, time consuming, inconsistent, human error prone, labor-intensive. It fails for mass production of the solar cell. This highlights the need of automated and reliable system for solar cell defect detection. The solar cell having various types of the defects including micro-cracks, finger interruptions, scratches, dark spots or stains, broken edges and chips, busbar defect etc. These defects are hampering the efficiency and life span of the solar cell. To overcome the manual mechanism limitations, the machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models have been used for automation of the defect detection process. It learns the complex patterns and able to recognize the defects accurately. The ML models lag in the detection of the complex patterns and speed along with various lightning conditions.

This research paper proposes the solution for above challenges. The YOLOv6 has been used for automated solar cell defect detection which can able to achieve the speed, optimization and robustness in the real time testing environment. Section II shows related work of the solar defect detection. Section III presents the proposed system architecture and module details. Section IV gives the proposed system implementation. Section V gives the results analysis using proposed approach, and its comparative study with Faster R-CNN and YOLOv5. Section VI gives the conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Different researchers are worked in the area of the solar panel defect detection using ML and DL techniques as follows –

R. Almashhadani, G. C. Hock, F. Hani Nordin, et al. [1] focuses on the defect in the PV using EL images. It uses ANN, CNN and SVM along with VGG16 for extraction of features. It uses the binary and multiclass classification mechanisms used for defect detection. VGG16 shows the highest results compared with others. Rana, N., Arora, S.

[2] mentioned the need of the automatic detection system by highlighting the drawbacks of manual system. It reviews various defects and the ML techniques applied on that. It can categories solar cell into non-defective and defective categories. Y. Guan et al., [3] proposed the MAGAN system for solar cell defect analysis. It uses the data augmentation to generate quality image which can further needed for the training and testing. It uses the CNN based model with MCA and GLSA modules for feature extraction and special attention. This model has been compared with other DL mechanisms. With the help of the model, the solar cell quality has been improved and reduces the defects. Wang Y, Guo J, Qi Y, et al. [4] compares the image processing, ML and DL based mechanisms and made analysis of it. It is found that the DL mechanism has more effectiveness than others. The simulation has been shown for them. The experimentation has been performed based on YOLOv8 and shows that it is having impressive results and speed of fault detection than others. Singh, O.D., Gupta, S. & Dora, S. [5] proposes the SVM based model for checking and identifying micro cracks on the solar cells. It has been tested on elpv dataset and tested on 2624 images. It gives good results as compared with the other systems. S. Tian, W. Li, S. Li, G. Tian, et al. [6] proposed the model with fusion of VGGNet and U-Net++. It takes the EL images and detects the faults. The convolution layer has been used and improved to get the performance. It also addressed the over-fitting of the data. The model is compared with the various other model for effect analysis with elpy dataset. R. Jaiswal, M. Martínez-Ramón and T. Busani [7] presents a overview of the ML mechanisms used in solar cells. The author is trying to discover the technique for the optimization. It also presents the challenges along with the improvements to be done. It can be improved in accuracy with minimization in cost of computing. B. Lipovšek, J. Krč and M. Topič, [8] investigated the light management mechanism using microtextural foils. The various sizes and shapes are analyzed with optimization. It can internally absorb the data and results shows the larger area is required. Shan Jin, YiLing Liu, ChenYun He [9] paper proposes the ML based mechanism for EL image based solar cell fault analysis. The EL images are preprocessed and extracted various features including contrast, brightness, grey etc. The fault has been extracted suing the LBP. ODT mechanism has been used for classification of defected surfaces. It accelerates the speed and accuracy of the detection. C. Xu, M. Famouri, G. Bathla, S. Nair, [10] proposes the CellDefectNet ML based mechanism for PV cell fault detection. It uses the edges for fault detection. Thios model has been tested on the various datasets and compared with the EfficientNet-80 mechanism. A. Phadke, N. Bhagwat, S. Mohaadkar, et al.

[11] proposes the solar cell fault detection suing CNN and YOLO. It analyzes the CV characteristics along with curves. The module can able to find the cracks, hotspots for improving the performance. It uses end to end monitoring and accessible for data management. The proposed model not only improves fault detection but provide robust solution. Youyang Wang, Liying Li, et al. [12] proposes the adaptive approach using unsupervised learning. It extracts the features form the EL images for recognition of the defect. It fine integrated with the classification mechanism. It provides the optimization solution to the PV solar cells. M. Zhang and L. Yin [13] propose the DL based solar cell fault recognition using YOLOv5. It is used for extracting complex background by using CSP module. IT uses ECA-net for enhancement. It adds the model improvement using Mosaic and MixUp. It also uses k mean's and CIOS using EL dataset.

From the above survey following are the limitations identified in the solar cell defect detection as follows -

- The datasets are suffering from imbalance in class; due to the various types of the panel, the generalization of dataset is required.
- Need to address the reflection, shadow and various lightening condition challenges.
- Need the speed in the defect detection step for improving detection of micro-defects.
- Optimizations need to considered inside the various mechanisms.

Therefore, it is clear that the there is a need of the system for solar cell defect detection in low light environment using the YOLO to makes all the process automatically without manual intervention.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig -1: Proposed System architecture for Solar Cell defect detection

The proposed system shown in fig. 1 represents the details of defect detection from the solar cell. It includes 4 stages as dataset collection, preprocessing, training & testing, and model evaluation. The system takes the camera input and dataset images. It also applies the preprocessing on the images including Mosaic, Flip, Scale, HSV and MixUp transformation to enhance the image quality and avoiding overfitting. The training and testing have been performed with the help of various DL mechanisms including Faster R CNN, YOLOv6 and YOLOv5. The various performance analysis parameters have been used for analyzing the performance of the model using elpv-dataset [17]. Following are the various modules used for design and implementation of the system as –

1.1 Data Collection

The input dataset has been collected for the solar cell images using EL imaging, visual cameras. For this research, elpv dataset has been downloaded from the public archive Kaggle.com [17]. It includes the 2624 images with 300*300 size. It uses 12 categories of the various defects including cracks, hotspots, broken fingers etc. These images are labeled and keep ready for the training.

1.2 Data Preprocessing

The various preprocessing techniques has been applied for over fitting as follows –

- Mosaic augmentation - It combines the various images into one to improve the object detection having variable scale.
- MixUp - It is used for images and labels of it for enhancing the generalization.
- Flip and Scale transform - It is used for creating the variations of the images into mirrored and resized image for diversification.
- HSV transform – It is used to adjust the HSV values of the images for adapting lightning changes. The

fig. 2 shows preprocessing operations on dataset.

Fig -2: Preprocessing the Dataset

Channel attention mechanism has been used for extraction of the various features from the images using YOLOv6. It can extract the various features related to edges, patterns, corners, etc.

1.3 Training & Testing

The training and testing of the dataset have been done using various DL mechanism including Faster R-CNN, YOLOv5 and YOLOv6. The YOLOv6 is the lightweight architecture and makes it suitable for real-time defect detection in the actual environment. It uses the many epochs are gives the output on textual and spatial features. The fig. 3 shows the graph of the accuracy versus epoch starting with 1 to 10 epoch.

1.4 Performance Analysis

The performance of the proposed system has been evaluated using various parameters as recall, accuracy, precision, F1-score values. The comparison of the YOLOv6, YOLOv5 and Faster R-CNN has been performed.

4. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The following are development details for implementation of the proposed system –

- Python (3.10.5) language
- IDE: Google Colab.
- Libraries: NumPy, TensorFlow, pandas, Matplotlib, and Scikit-learn
- Dataset – elpv [17]

The fig. 4 shows the snap of the proposed system of solar cell defect detection. It train the dataset using various algorithms such as YOLOv5, YOLOv6 and Faster R-CNN. It can bale to identify the defect automatically.

Fig -4: Actual defect detection snap of solar cell

5. RESULT ANALYSIS

Three different algorithms including Faster R-CNN, YOLOv5 and YOLOv6 have been tested for various analysis parameters including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and mAP. Table 1 shows the performance of various algorithm used for training and their performance analysis.

Table 1 Result Analysis for object detection using YOLOv5, Faster RCNN and YOLOv6

Parameter	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	Accuracy (%)	F1-score (%)	mAP (%)
Faster R-CNN	89.71	91.07	90.09	89.95	91.78
YOLOv5	90.76	92.56	92.14	91.45	92.23
YOLOv6	99.21	98.82	99.04	99	98.42

Fig. 5 Performance analysis of Faster R-CNN, YOLOv5, and YOLOv6

The fig. 5 shows the result comparison of all the models. Within all three models, the YOLOv6 gives the higher performance compared with other two. It gives precision of 99.21%, recall of 98.82%, accuracy of 99.04%, F1-score of 99%, and mAP of 98.42%. This indicates that the YOLOv6 showing the high reliability with less false detection for solar cell defect detection. These results are achieved due to architecture improvement, efficient extraction of features during training.

YOLOv5 shows impressive performance with precision of 90.76% and recall of 92.56%, resulting in an F1-score of 91.45% and mAP of 92.23%. The YOLOv5 slightly lags in the complex defect patterns and optimization. Faster R- CNN shows lower performance and slow speed comparatively than YOLO with an accuracy of 90.09% and mAP of 91.78%.

Overall, the YOLOv6 outperforms than both YOLOv5 and faster R-CNN across all evaluation parameters. So, it is suitable for the real-time fault detection inside the manufacturing plant of solar cell.

5. CONCLUSION

In recent years, solar energy has been used for the generating sustainable source of the clean energy. The solar cell makes it possible to generate the energy by capturing the rays on the surface. These cells often face the defects during mass manufacturing process. Traditionally manual mechanism has been used for defect observation by eyes, but is often error prone and time consuming. So, the automated mechanism has been developed using the ML and DL mechanism. The proposed research focuses on the design and development of the fault detection mechanism using YOLOv6 mechanism for robust, speedy and automatic defect recognition from the solar cell surface. It uses the preprocessing and feature extraction phases. It has been compared with the other mechanism including faster R- CNN and YOLOv5. YOLOv6 based model shows the higher performance compared with other two as precision (99.21%), recall (98.82%), accuracy (99.04%), F1-score (99%), and mAP (98.42%). This proves that the YOLOv6 provides the efficient and reliable solution for the defect recognition and most suitable for mass production plants. In the future the system has been extended with inclusion of the following modifications towards developing robust defect detection approach with integrated with various edge and embedded devices for real time processing without latency. YOLOv9 or hybrid versions of the DL can be used for accuracy enhancement.

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